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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **O**Live and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 6.2

Co-designed climate services communication and exploitation indicators n°1

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Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The objective of this deliverable D6.2 – “Co-designed Climate Services Communication and Exploitation Indicators Report n.1” is to primarily report on the project’s communication and exploitation activities and at the same time build upon deliverable 7.1 – “Communication, dissemination, and exploitation management plan” by presenting additions to the initial strategy that will be reinforced during the project lifetime.

Finally, it is important mentioning that this document reflects the current status of the technological developments. At the time of release, the ICT platform and most of the MED-GOLD services are still under development, and technical decisions must be taken in the following months, which will have a significant impact in the current communication and exploitation plan. Deliverable 6.14 is expected to contain the final description of a MED-GOLD exploitation plan.

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, Part B Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. PURPOSE AND SCOPE

This document provides in detail the dissemination and exploitation indicators during the first period of the project (M01 to M24). The grounding of such activities was clearly defined and guided by both the Description of Action (DoA) and Deliverable (D) 7.1 – Communication, dissemination, and exploitation management plan.

The purpose of the current deliverable is therefore two-folded: 1) to report on the MED-GOLD project's dissemination and exploitation indicators conducted between month 1 to month 24 and 2) to present additions to the initial strategy that will be reinforced during the project lifetime.

The remaining part of this document is organised as follows:

- Section 3.1 provides a summary of MED-GOLD with the purpose of introducing the project to the reader.
- Section 3.2 provides the communication and dissemination indicators and activities during the first period of the project.
- Section 3.3 provides exploitation indicators together with an update of the exploitation strategy.

1.2. DEFINITIONS AND ACRONYMS

1.2.1. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-1 Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Business Model	The concept of the business model in the literature on information systems and business refers to ways of creating value for customers, and to the way in which a business turns market opportunity into profit through sets of actors, activities and collaboration.
Exploitation	The utilization of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities.
Climate Service	Timely production and delivery (translation and transfer) in customized products (projections, forecasts, information, trends, economic analysis, assessments, etc.) of useful climate-related data, information and knowledge that support adaptation, mitigation and disaster risk management to decision makers
Communication	Strategic and targeted measures for promoting the results to a multitude of audiences
Dissemination	Public disclosure of the results by an appropriate communication channel.
End-user	Organization or person who ultimately uses or is intended to ultimately use a product or service
Key Performance Indicators	Measurable value that demonstrates the effectiveness of an activity
Plan	Detailed proposal or scheme agreed within parts of acting, doing, proceeding and/or making.
Result	Tangible or intangible output (data, knowledge or information)
User	Organization or person who support, maintain, procure, authorize or pay a product or service

1.2.2. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-2 Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CS	Creative Service
EIP-AGRI	Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
EU	European Union
EYPL	European Union Public Licence
GA	Grant Agreement
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies

Acronym	Definition
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MED-GOLD	Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, OLive and Durum wheat food systems
MGs	MED-GOLD partners
PR	Public Relation
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

2. REFERENCES

2.1. REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Table 2-1 Reference Documents

Ref.	Title	Date
[RD.1]	MED-GOLD Grant Agreement	16-10-2017
[RD.2]	MED-GOLD Quality Plan	23-04-2017
[RD.3]	D6.22 Summary of dissemination and communication activities n°2	06-11-2019
[RD.4]	D7.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan	31-05-2018

3. DOCUMENT CONTENT

3.1. SUMMARY OF MED-GOLD

3.1.1. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Climate change is causing new patterns in climatic conditions over the world, which are already affecting many aspects of our society. Though being a global phenomenon, nowhere else in the world is Climate Change expected to have ecological, economic and social consequences as dramatic as those in the Mediterranean basin. Higher than average projected changes in climate and shifting weather patterns endanger an extremely rich and intertwined biological diversity, which supports human activities such as farming. In this context, the agriculture sector in particular is especially threatened, as it is largely climate-driven and thus highly vulnerable to its variability.

The risk of crop failure and pest damage, as well as natural hazards such as heat waves, storms or floods is likely to increase, requiring immediate action to be undertaken to adapt to this uncertain outlook. The challenge is to develop tools to build more resilient, efficient and sustainable agriculture and food systems. To that end, the development of climate services to support decision-making and best practice in agriculture is essential.

That is why the aim of MED-GOLD is to translate state-of-the-art climate data and climate predictions — at the seasonal timescale and beyond — into easily accessible, valuable information for a wide range of end-users in the agriculture sector.

3.1.2. CLIMATE SERVICES

Within the European Commission (EC), the field of climate services has been identified as one of the few “flagship initiatives” of key areas of public interest in which to invest with priority during Horizon 2020. In this context, the term ‘Climate Services’ has a broad meaning: transforming climate-related data and other information into customized products such as projections, trends, economic analysis, advice on best practices, development and evaluation of solutions, and any other climate-related service liable to benefit that may be of use for the society at large. These services include data, information and knowledge that support adaptation, mitigation and disaster risk management. MED-GOLD will provide Climate Services for grape, olives and durum wheat sectors. The new services will be the result of the upgrading, tailoring and integration of existing modelling platforms. Innovative tools will be developed for the management of risks associated with the spread of noxious organisms, yield and quality losses and other climate related threats for crops. Importantly, these services will offer support for decision making at two different timescales: a shorter (seasonal) one, as well as a longer outlook over the next few decades.

All the new tools will be gathered into a single data interface platform for maximizing accessibility and ease of use for the end-users, as well as to generate synergies that can be reaped from common issues shared by the three agricultural sectors.

3.2. COMMUNICATION INDICATORS AND STRATEGY

3.2.1. OBJECTIVES

Dissemination, communication and exploitation activities are essential to ensure the success of MED-GOLD and are closely coordinated among the various work packages to ensure a cohesive plan of action that will create large scale impact in the Climate Change scene and in a global perspective. In order to widen the outreach of the project's efforts and maximise the impact that MED-GOLD activities will have, the consortium pursues and ensures close coordination with the European Commission, the various ongoing Climate Change projects and other relevant initiatives in closely linked domains, such as Copernicus, CLARA, etc.

In this respect, MED-GOLD gradually and systematically builds up and mobilises a community with major players on the Climate Change scene including innovators, researchers, big, medium and small businesses, committed to adopting and exploiting the project's outcomes in a sustainable way by embracing nationally and internationally related efforts. The main idea is to involve a critical mass of relevant stakeholders early in the project by properly tuning promotional and marketing activities and by keeping them engaged through a continuous and dynamic approach.

The main objectives of MED-GOLDs communication strategy and activities are to:

- Reach, stimulate and engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders.
- Generate broad awareness for the European Climate Change community about MED-GOLD work and services, with the purpose of attracting them to participate to the MED-GOLD community.
- Ensure broad visibility of the project's work and disseminate results to the Climate Change community and beyond.

3.2.2. COMMUNICATION TARGET AUDIENCE AND CHANNELS

Deliverable 7.1 segments the target audience on four separate groups:

- Upper level: Scientific and technical community or networks, Public agencies and authorities, Investments banks, Assurance companies and NGOs.
- Intermediate level: Climate service providers and purveyors, Information providers, Environmental-agriculture consultancy and advisory service companies, Engineering firms, Nongovernmental organizations and Sectorial organizations or associations.
- End-user level: Large-scale producers, local professional organizations, small agricultural business and Farmers.
- General Public.

At the same time, in MED-GOLD's communication plan and strategy a description a plethora of communication channels is already defined, in order to effectively reach the targets groups and to maximize awareness of the overall project's work and outcome. The synergy of MED-GOLD dissemination is generated through seamless connected online and offline communication activities. Both online (e.g. website and social media) and offline channels (e.g. public events) will be used to disseminate the related activities and project actions throughout Europe and beyond. In addition, all the networks and multiplier channels allow the partners of MED-GOLD to raise the visibility of the project's achievements and to reach a critical mass of stakeholders, developers, contributors, integrators, researchers and relevant key players for an efficient implementation of the project work plan. The dissemination channels used to reach each target group are detailed in Table 3.1.

Table 3-1 Communication Channels per target group

Channel	General Public	End-User Level	Intermediate Level	Upper Level
Website	X	X	X	X
Social Networks	X	X	X	X
Newsletters	X	X	X	X
MED-GOLD Workshops	X	X	X	X
Scientific Publications			X	X
PR materials	X	X	X	X
Forum	X	X	X	X
General Media	X	X		

3.2.3. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

During the first period of the project, MED-GOLD has been involved in several dissemination and communication activities. The consortium has ensured a fruitful promotion of the Project and its results, including the following:

- Creating the project Logo and identity
- Generating and maintaining the MED-GOLD website
- Contributing to the project Twitter account
- Developing and distributing the newsletters
- Organizing Summer Schools
- Organizing Workshops
- Publishing, submitting and presenting scientific papers
- Creating promotional materials

It is essential to point out that the consortium has been very dynamic in identifying multichannel approaches to increase the impact of the Dissemination and Communication activities.

At the same time several actions have been undertaken to ensure the internal communication between the partners of the project:

- Annual General Assemblies.
- Monthly Work Package virtual meetings.
- An internal area on the Project's website, a private online workspace dedicated to project management, including reporting and nonpublic information, has been designed with the purpose to facilitate partner collaboration.

3.2.4. QUANTITATIVE INDICATORS

In Table 3.2 the communication indicators as measured in M24 are being quoted.

Table 3-2 KPIs for Communication and dissemination

Item	KPIs and Target Value	Measured Value
MED-GOLD Website	About 5,000 user sessions per year (data to be collected through Google analytics or similar systems). The website will be maintained for at least one year after the termination of the project.	The MED-GOLD website (https://www.med-gold.eu) counts above 500 sessions per month for the first year and above 600 per month for the second year which corresponds to above 13000 user sessions (data from Google Analytics) A twitter account (@medgold_h2020) has been also set up and is actively fed to enhance the outreach.
Stakeholders' Database	A list of about 500 stakeholders involved in agrifood-related domains, policy- and decision makers, academia, regional/local authorities, industry, investors, etc.	The list of stakeholders includes 152 contacts as of November 2019. More specifically: Agrifood in general: 60 Grapes/wine sector: 50 Olives/Olive Oil sector: 23 Durum Wheat/ Pasta sector: 17 Climate sector: 3 Other: 3 Total: 152 (some stakeholder registered for more than one sector, which is why these numbers do not add up to 152 exactly)
Newsletters and content (articles, press releases, infosheets)	Two eNewsletter released per year targeting a community of 500 stakeholders (to be reached at the end of the project). Distribution of at least 6 press and news releases and at least 4 articles/interviews to the general and specialised media, portals, blogs and promoted via social media with hundreds of take-ups each. Six infosheets available on the website, distributed via social media and through 1-to-1 direct mailing to the specific target groups. At least 4 journalistic articles/interviews.	Newsletters: 2 (newsletter 1 sent to 51 members and newsletter 2 sent to 116 members) Articles (on the project website): 11 Articles (in press): 41 Articles (institutional websites): 13 Interviews: 2 Infosheets: 3 (in 6 languages)
Handout materials	MED-GOLD flyer and e-handbook will be both browsable through the website and available in printable format for public download. The flyer in English and in local languages will be printed and distributed during the events.	Flyer: 1 E-handbook: 0
Participation in conferences	MED-GOLD will target the participation in 10 major international conferences events (fairs, conferences, exhibitions, etc.) in the course of the project.	Events:42
Events (online & offline)	3 webinars will be organised. Expected participants: minimum 30 per webinar. Organisation of a final event with stakeholders (format to be decided) at the end of the project to present the project's results.	Webinar: 1 (18 participants)
Use of partners' network	MED-GOLD will take advantage of the partners' existing communication channels and networks to disseminate and communicate its results. Examples are the partners' newsletters, their websites and platforms, their social media accounts and magazines. Outreach: 2000-3000 users	Partners are actively using their social media, web platforms and connections with local events and relevant projects to communicate and disseminate MED-GOLD. The direct engagement with users will start at a later stage in the projects, when the sectoral tools will be in a more advanced stage of development.
Mobilization of Stakeholder Associations, support from the Advisory Board members and other EU projects and initiatives	Associations provide direct communication channels into the target groups the MEDGOLD is trying to penetrate. These include all the associations and initiatives the partners are members of, as well as the members of the Advisory Board. Besides that, other EU initiatives providing communication support to EU funded projects as well as other EU funded projects will be approached to exploit synergies and jointly organized actions.	Climate Service Initiatives engaged: 15 Agricultural Initiatives engaged: 12
Scientific/technical publications	The target is 10 scientific papers in high impact journals, and 10 scientific papers in high reputation International Conferences.	Scientific papers: 1 published, 2 in press

3.3. EXPLOITATION INDICATORS

The exploitation plan already described in deliverable 7.1 ensures that MED-GOLD results will create the opportunity to market innovative products and services, promote new research and support policy making. The list of exploitable results of MED-GOLD per sector is presented in Table 3-3. The expected exploitation results per partner of the consortium are listed in Table 3-4.

Table 3-3 List of exploitable results

Sector	Climate Services Description
Olive / Olive Oil	Olive fruit fly infestation models for short and long-term time scales Olive yield modelling approaches for seasonal and projections
Grapes / Wine	Short- and long-term analysis of relevant climatic, bioclimatic and extreme climate indices affecting field management operations (choice of plantation site, grapevine variety, setting harvest dates, operational farming planning)
Durum Wheat / Pasta	Seasonal and long-time scale forecasting for yield, risk of diseases and operational farming management

Table 3-4 Exploitation result expectations by each partner

Partner	Expectations	Type of exploitable project result	Sector	Target market
ENEA	Establish an exploitable network for climate services in key agricultural sector for Italy	Networking / Knowledge	Public	National (Italy)
BARILLA	Implement in their operational system the climate services developed for durum wheat Develop a business plan to promote the capitalization of the results and to facilitate the application of the developed technologies at farms, storage facilities and milling plants	Knowledge / Product-Service	Private	Local (Italy)
Beetobit	Developing and maintaining large-scale cloud infrastructure	Networking / Knowledge	Private	European / Global
BSC	Extend and implement new tools related to seasonal predictions and climatic indicators	Knowledge	Public / Private	European / Global
CNR	Improve methodologies to obtain high accuracy and robust data products for seasonal forecasts	Knowledge	Public	European / Global
DCOOP	Improve their advice services to farmers and cooperatives based on climate services	Knowledge / Product-Service	Private	Local (Spain)
ec2ce	Exploit climate services innovation in their activity	Knowledge / Product-Service	Private	European / Global
GMV	Extend and exploit climate services in other regions and sector based on project experience	Knowledge / Product-Service / Networking	Private	European / Global
HORTA	Implement in their system granoduro.net® the pilot climate service developed Exploit climate services innovation in their activity	Knowledge / Product-Service	Private	National / European
JRC	Innovate on its agro-climatic modelling systems and provide more robust, reliable and consistent evidences for the agro-climatic policy support	Dissemination / Knowledge	Public	European / Global
Met Office	Increase knowledge on climatic and bioclimatic indicators	Networking / Knowledge	Public	European / Global
NOA	Promotion of professional workshops for capacity building and participation on international conferences	Networking / Knowledge	Public	European / Global

Partner	Expectations	Type of exploitable project result	Sector	Target market
SOGRAPE	Improve and develop climate services for its viticulture activity	Knowledge / Product-Service	Private	Local (Portugal)
UnivLeeds	Publications of peer-review articles and participation on international conferences	Dissemination	Public	European / Global
UTH	Capacity building of graduate and undergraduate studies in climate services and acquire practical experience	Knowledge / Dissemination / Networking	Public	Global

Since MED-GOLD has been building the foundations upon which scientific results are going to be produced or in some cases such results have only recently been produced, it wasn't possible to exploit those results by the partners of this consortium. This will be the scope of the successor of this document, deliverable 6.14 "Co-designed Climate Services Communication and Exploitation Indicators Report n.2".

3.3.1. S.W.O.T. ANALYSIS FOR MED-GOLD

In this section we perform a SWOT analysis, as an addition to the exploitation strategy of MED-GOLD. The present SWOT analysis (SWOT standing for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) tries to answer the following questions:

- **Strengths:** What works in favour of MED-GOLD and the Climate Change community? What unique resources can the Project draw on? What do its diverse stakeholders see as its strengths? What policy factors are associated with these strengths?
- **Weaknesses:** What could be improved in favour of MED-GOLD and the Climate Change community? What are the sources of these weaknesses? What is necessary to alleviate those weaknesses?
- **Opportunities:** What opportunities are open MED-GOLD and the Climate Change community? What trends could it take advantage of? How can we turn Projects strengths into opportunities? What is necessary to better address these opportunities?
- **Threats:** What threats could harm MED-GOLD and the Climate Change community? What alternatives are offered? What threats do these weaknesses expose? What policy-related interventions are required to address these threats?

In Table 3.5 we quote a SWOT analysis of MED-GOLD.

Table 3-5 S.W.O.T Analysis of MED-GOLD

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>The consortium consists of multidisciplinary partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The presence of the three industrial problem holders ensures an unprecedented expertise in understating the needs of the sectors of interest. • Scientific partners that already possess the know-how on Climate Change and are capable of creating state of the art Climate Services. • IT partners that provide the needed support by creating and maintaining the required infrastructure. <p>There is a wide spread of publicly available climate data that MED-GOLD can use. At the same time collaboration with already established projects provides added value to the Project. Also, partners provide their datasets and tools to MED-GOLD.</p> <p>The general public and policy makers now more than ever acknowledge the need for Climate Change actions, in order to adapt to the effects of Climate Change.</p> <p>Decision makers, especially in the agrifood sector, are seeing the effects of Climate Change to their business and are willing to use scientific knowledge into their planning processes.</p>	<p>It is possible that the full vision of the project may require much more resources than those available to the project. MED-GOLD needs to plan carefully and focus on the resources that are deemed more important.</p> <p>Complexity of stakeholders. From MED-GOLD core users to the Local, national and international general public, MED-GOLD might be too ambitious in trying to communicate with those different types of stakeholders. It is considered mandatory to use different communication techniques according to the target audience.</p>

Opportunities	Threats
<p>Since the impact of Climate Change is affecting more and more our lives, there are opportunities that derive from that fact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The industry needs to integrate the climate dimension in their strategic, operational and planning processes due to Climate Change disruptive impacts over their production. • The general public is understanding the impacts of Climate Change now more than ever, which provides the needed pressure so that legislators start acting. • Policies are already being implemented across Europe and are driven by a high level of persuasion that the impacts of Climate Change must be mitigated. But policies at a greater scope are needed. • Climate change mitigation and its close relationship with agro-alimentary sector is a growing need with global repercussion. 	<p>There are two types of threats related to MED-GOLD, threats that come from outside the MED-GOLD community:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The status quo of the Energy Industry is against any Climate Change initiatives and resists the most to the reforms that are mandatory. • Stakeholders do not understand Climate Services as a primary need, compared to weather forecasts. <p>And threats from within the MED-GOLD community:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The consortium multidisciplinary although is a strength, also poses a threat to the success of the project, because there is a chance that it might cause miscommunication between them. Since all partners of the consortium have considerable experience in multidisciplinary projects this threat is not expected to become a problem. • MED-GOLD trying to create a community and not reaching a critical mass can be considered a failure and pose a threat to the project. Proper communication and dissemination techniques must be used during lifespan of the project. • User expectations exceeding the scientific state-of-the-art may deter adoption and interest in climate services if not adequately communicated. Measures to define the best communication methods for building user trust are developed during the project timeline.

4. CONCLUSION

This document reports on the MED-GOLD project's dissemination and exploitation indicators and activities conducted during the first period of the Project (month 1 to month 24) and presents additions to the initial strategy that will be reinforced during the project lifetime.

END OF DOCUMENT

